

Short communication

First records of *Leptoglossus occidentalis* Heidemann, 1910 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Coreidae) in Latvia

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Abstract. The first records of *Leptoglossus occidentalis* Heidemann, 1910 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Coreidae) for Latvia are reported. Additional information on the findings is given.

Key words: true bugs, western conifer seed bug, distribution, new records, invasive species, Baltic states.

Recently, the highly dispersible Nearctic coreid *Leptoglossus occidentalis* Heidemann, 1910 was reported from Lithuania (Karalius & Karaliūtė 2019) and Estonia (van der Heyden 2021). The gap between these two Baltic countries is closed in this note by reporting the first records of the species from Latvia.

So far, five specimens of *L. occidentalis* have been found in Latvia. Photographs of the specimens and specific data on the findings were uploaded to the online database Dabasdati.lv:

1. - **03.10.2020**, Salaspils city, Miera street (Lat. 56.861800, Long. 24.365300), on curtains inside an apartment, photographed by Lilija Vanaga.
2. - **23.01.2021**, ~1 km W Kolka village (Lat. 57.744700, Long. 22.570800), lying on the snow in a pine forest, photographed by Mareks Ieviņš.
3. - **23.01.2021**, ~1,2 km NW Kolka village (Lat. 57.749400, Long. 22.569800), lying on the snow in a pine forest, photographed by Mareks Ieviņš.
4. - **24.01.2021**, ~1 km NW Virsīte village (Lat. 56.350900, Long. 23.900600), lying on the snow in a mixed forest, photographed by Valda Ērmāne.
5. - **02.04.2021**, between Sikrags and Mazirbe villages (Lat. 57.661500, Long. 22.262600), beaten from a *Juni-perus communis* L. (Cupressaceae) bush in a pine forest, leg. Mareks Ieviņš (Fig. 1).

The three specimens observed on 23.01.2021 and 24.01.2021 were found at air temperatures of 2–4° C, seemingly ‘frozen’/still and not moving (Mareks Ieviņš and Valda Ērmāne, personal communication).

Fig. 1. Specimen of *Leptoglossus occidentalis* Heidemann, 1910 found between Sikrags and Mazirbe villages – photo by Mareks Ieviņš.

The localities of the findings are marked in green in a square map based on 10 km x 10 km grid cells (Fig. 2). They might indicate that *L. occidentalis* is more widespread in the western part of Latvia. Further research might lead to more knowledge on this issue.

Fig. 2. Known distribution of *Leptoglossus occidentalis* Heidemann, 1910 in Latvia.

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References

- Karalius S., Karaliūtė A. 2019. First record of the invasive western conifer seed bug *Leptoglossus occidentalis* (Heteroptera, Coreidae) in Lithuania. *Lietuvos entomologų draugijos darbai* **3 (31)**: 17–18.
- van der Heyden T. 2021. First records of *Leptoglossus occidentalis* Heidemann, 1910 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Coreidae) in Estonia and Belarus. *Heteroptera Poloniae – Acta Faunistica* **15**: 5–6.

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